

C ++ Language in Code :: Block Based Distribution Sharing Automation

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ABSTRACT

Dividing inheritance into probelmatika in each region, because it is not yet understood by Islamic law about the distribution of inheritance. Therefore, this research was made to make it easier for people to use the C ++ language in the codeblock application. The results of this study are that the distribution of inheritance using C ++ based on codeblock is more efficient and does not cause conflicts between families, because it is according to shari'ah calculations.

Keyword ; Pembagian Waris, C++, Distributions

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background

The inheritance law is the one that regulates the transfer of assets of a person who has died and the consequences for the heirs. Ash-Shabuni said that the legal inheritance of all types of property or ownership left by the heir, both in the form of money, land, and so on. The law of inheritance in Islam is often referred to as *farāid*, because the portion of each heir has been determined by Shari'a.

In addition, Islamic inheritance law is also often named as the science of *mawāriś* because it talks about the transfer of inherited property of the deceased to people who are still alive. The inheritance law according to the compilation of Islamic Law in Article 171 (a) is that which regulates the transfer of ownership rights to the inheritance (*tirkah*) of the heir, determining who is entitled to be an heir and some of their respective parts. This definition is in line with what was

stated by Hasbi Ash-Shiddieqy and Muhammad Muhyiddin.

In this case will apply the calculation of the distribution of the right inheritance according to Islamic law. So that it simplifies the distribution process, as it should.

B. Formulation

Berdasarkan paparan latar belakang diatas maka dapat ditarik sebuah rumusan masalah yaitu bagaimana mengotomatisasi perhitungan pembagian harta waris menurut islam.

C. Aim

Mengaplikasikan perhitungan pembagian harta waris yang benar menurut *syari'*, agar tidak menimbulkan konflik antar keluarga.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Theoretical Basis

- a. Treasures in Islam are things that are important enough to be able to carry

out life in the world as well as achieving the afterlife.

- b. C ++, is a computer programming language created by Bjarne Stroustrup, which is a development of the C language developed by Dennis Ritchie in the early 1970s. (Dennis Ritchie)
- c. Programming algorithms are a logical sequence of steps to solve a problem. This is clarified in a logical / reasonable sequence of steps, which means that the algorithm must follow a sequence and steps and should not be jumped. Or arranged systematically. (Andy Prasetyo, ST., M.Kom)
- d. Inheritance generally means the transfer of property from the deceased party to another person who is his heir.

2.2. Research Relevan

There are several related studies regarding the distribution of inheritance in Islam:

Kadir Jaelani Abdul, Pulungan (2013) "Views of Law and Ulama Experts in Malang City on the principle of legality in the distribution of inheritance assets, bro." Master thesis, Islamic University of Maulana Malik Ibrahim.

In this study the results achieved:

"According to the Malang City Law and Ulama expert regarding the

principle of legalization in the distribution of inheritance assets, this is a very important legality for the distribution of inheritance assets in written form where a statement from a notary official can be made or a request to the Religious Court to determine heirs so that later it will facilitate the distribution of inheritance. "

"Related to being used as a statement of the distribution of inheritance assets as a marriage requirement for widowers / divorced widows in order to avoid differences of opinion."

Afijal, S.Kom "The support system for deciding inheritance assets according to Islamic law uses Visual Basic 6.0" Thesis Megister Komputer, Putra Indonesia University (UPI) "YPTK" Padang.

In this study the results achieved:

"The application-based system that is designed can help heirs calculate the legacy left behind even without expert assistance using Visual Basic 6.0 Software and Microsoft Access database."

"The output of this system is information received by the heirs based on the determination of the calculation of inheritance according to Islamic law."

Fikri and Wahidin, 2016 "Concepts of the Law of Inheritance of Islam and the Law of Waris Adat

(Analosisi contextualization in Bugis Society)" STAIN Parepare Students

In this study the results achieved:

"Islamic inheritance law stipulated by Allah SWT, is neatly and systematically regulated, especially the provisions concerning who has the right and not, the provisions concerning each part of the heirs so as not to trigger disputes that can ultimately aim for the breakdown of family ties."

"The contextualization of the implementation of inheritance law in Bugis society occurs because of the process of assimilation in the application of Islamic law and customary law. Both law enforcement are difficult to separate in people's lives and are considered not contradictory to one another in application. "

3. Research Method

The stages in the study are as follows:

- a. Data collection
- b. Initial data processing
- c. Grouping
- d. Stages of the proposed method
- e. Experiments and research testing
- f. Research evaluation and validation
- g. Results of research accuracy

The method proposed in this study is C ++ Language Programming Based on CodeBlock in the distribution of inheritance according to Islamic law:

1. Collect data on inheritance recipient families (Heirs)
2. Calculating the total amount of Muwaris inheritance (the person who died)
3. Calculation of arimatika distribution of inheritance based on the order of recipients / heirs

CAUSE / RELATIONSHIP	EXPERTISE	REQUIREMENTS	HE EXTENSION OF HERITAGE
MERITAL (still bound by status)	Husband	If there are no children / grandchildren	1/2 Part
		If there are children / grandchildren	1/4 Part
	Wife	If there are no children / grandchildren	1/4 Part
		If there are children / grandchildren	1/8 Part
RELATIONSHIP	Son	Alone or have another child / grandchild	Ashobah (the rest of all assets after the other division is divided)
		Note : division between male and female 2: 1	
	Doughter	Alone or have another child / grandchild	1/2 Part
		Have a brother (sister)	2/3 Part
	Biological father	Alone or have another child / grandchild	1/3 Part
		have another child / grandchild	1/6 Part
	Biological Mother	If there are no children / grandchildren and widows (no Husband / biological father)	1/3 Part
		If there are no children / grandchildren but there is a husband (biological father)	1/3 from the husband's quota (biological father)
		If there are children / grandchildren and widows (no Husband / biological father)	1/6 Part

The following is the course flow of the program:

Flowchart Sistem

IV. Result & Discussion

Arithmetic used in this study is a formula according to Shari 'and determined by the Government.

Table 4.1 Datasheet Sample

MUWARI S	TOTAL TREASURE OF WARIS (Rp.)	JUMLAH AHLI WARIS					
		HUSBAND	Wife	Son	Daughter	Father	Mother
DARMO	Rp 100.000.000	-	1	1	1	-	1

Following are the steps in calculating inheritance according to Islamic law with manual calculations:

1. Collect data on families who receive inheritance (heirs)
 - a. Husband: -
 - b. Wife: 1
 - c. Child (lk): 1
 - d. Child (pr): 1
 - e. Other families: biological mothers

2. Calculation of inheritance distribution

a. Istri :

$$\frac{1}{8} \times 100.000.000 = \text{Rp } 12.500.000$$

3. Ibu (kdg) :

$$\frac{1}{6} \times 100.000.000 = \text{Rp } 16.667.000 +$$

$$\text{Rp } 29.167.000$$

4. Ashobah :

$$100.000.000 - 29.167.000 = \text{Rp } 70.833.000$$

5. Anak (lk) :

$$\text{Ashobah (2:1 dari anak pr)} = \text{Rp } 47.222.000$$

6. Anak (pr) :

$$\text{Ashobah (1:2 dari anak lk)} = \text{Rp } 23.611.000$$

So the arithmetic calculations above are in accordance with the existing provisions.

```

main.cpp
5 int main()
6 {
7     char nama[50], family[20], suami, istri, pesutri;
8     int anak1, anak2, a, b, c, d, e, f, total;
9     double muwaris;
10    cout << "===== PROGRAM PEMBAGIAN HARTA WARIS =====<< endl;
11    cout << "Nama :< < endl;
12    cout << "      Qish :< < endl;
13    cout << "=====< < endl;
14    cout << "Masukan Nama Muwaris :< < endl;
15    cout << "Total Harta yang dikembalikan (Rp) :< < endl;
16    cout << "Ahlil Waris :< < endl;
17    cout << "Anak (lk) :< < endl;
18    cout << "Anak (pr) :< < endl;
19    cout << "Keluarga Lain :< < endl;
20    cout << "Ayah kandung :< < endl;
21    cout << "Ibu kandung :< < endl;
22    cout << "Status Muwaris (suami/istri) :< < endl;
23    cout << "=====< < endl;
24
  
```

Source Opening Code Program

The following is an automation program for the distribution of inheritance

Prediction Variable

a = Husband

b = Wife

c = Son

d = Daughter

e = Father

f = Mother

Asobah = (total asset – husband/wife – father – mother)

Son = 2:1 or 2/3 ashobah

Daughter = 1/3 ashobah

```
24
25 if (muwaris==suami){
26     d=0.125*total;
27     e=0.375*total;
28     f=0.17*total;
29     c=0.67*(total-b-e-f)/anak1;
30     d=0.17*(total-b-e-f)/anak2;
31     cout << " Hakisan yang diperoleh Istri" << endl;
32     cout << " Anak (lk) = Rp " << c << endl;
33     cout << " Anak (pr) = Rp " << d << endl;
34     cout << " Ayah = Rp " << e << endl;
35     cout << " Ibu = Rp " << f << endl;
36 } else
37 if (muwaris==istri){
38     a=0.25*total;
39     e=0.375*total;
40     f=0.17*total;
41     c=0.67*(total-a-e-f)/anak1;
42     d=0.17*(total-a-e-f)/anak2;
43     cout << " Hakisan yang diperoleh Suami" << endl;
44     cout << " Anak (lk) = Rp " << c << endl;
45     cout << " Anak (pr) = Rp " << d << endl;
46     cout << " Ayah = Rp " << e << endl;
47     cout << " Ibu = Rp " << f << endl;
48 }
49 return 0;
50
51
```

Result Distributions Source Coding

The following are compiling results from the Bidikmisi student graduation prediction program using code :: block by running the program and then entering the text that is in accordance with the provisions

```
C:\Users\LABKOM-01\Downloads\abu\123\bin\Debug\123.exe
-----
PROGRAM PEMBAGIAN HARTA WARIS
Oleh : ABU NIZZAN ADAMI
-----
Masukan Nama Muwaris      : Akhdad Busrom
Total Harta yang diwariskan (Rp) : Rp 100000000
Ahli Waris
Anak (lk)                  : 1
Anak (pr)                  : 1
Keluarga Lain             :
Ayah Kandung              : ada
Ibu Kandung                : ada
Status Muwaris (suami/istri) : suami
-----
Warisan yang diperoleh Istri = Rp 12500000
Anak (lk)                   = Rp 25125000
Anak (pr)                   = Rp 6375000
Ayah                        = Rp 33000000
Ibu                          = Rp 17000000
-----
Process returned 0 (0x0)   execution time : 87.968 s
Press any key to continue.
```

Source Code Running Console Compiling

```
C:\Users\LABKOM-01\Downloads\abu\123\bin\Debug\123.exe
-----
PROGRAM PEMBAGIAN HARTA WARIS
Oleh : ABU NIZZAN ADAMI
-----
Masukan Nama Muwaris      : Ade Nur Azizah
Total Harta yang diwariskan (Rp) : Rp 100000000
Ahli Waris
Anak (lk)                  : 2
Anak (pr)                  : 1
Keluarga Lain             :
Ayah Kandung              : ada
Ibu Kandung                : ada
Status Muwaris (suami/istri) : istri
-----
Warisan yang diperoleh Suami = Rp 12500000
Anak (lk)                   = Rp 12562500
Anak (pr)                   = Rp 6375000
Ayah                        = Rp 33000000
Ibu                          = Rp 17000000
-----
Process returned 0 (0x0)   execution time : 38.101 s
Press any key to continue.
```

Running Console Program

Note. Amount of acquisition of child after divided by 2

The calculation carried out looks at the total assets divided by the number of heir data, which will then be obtained by each of the heirs.

5. Conclusions & Suggestions

Based on the above research using C++ code-based language :: block to divide inheritance can increase the accuracy of calculations and time efficiency so as to minimize the occurrence of inter-family conflicts.

Before doing calculations it is recommended to ask the main heirs (husband / wife) so as not to cause conflict.

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